

Clustering and Machine Learning algorithms as tools to support groundwater management in water-stressed areas. Application in the agricultural region of Campo de Dalías (Almería, Spain)

Miguel Ángel Díaz¹, Lupicinio García¹, Francisco Núñez¹, Manuel Argamasilla¹, José Manuel Nieto¹, Damián Sánchez¹

¹Fundación Centro Andaluz de Investigaciones del Agua – Cetaqua Andalucía, Málaga (Spain)
miguelangel.diaz@cetaqua.com

ABSTRACT

The semi-arid regions of the Mediterranean coast, such as Campo de Dalías and Sierra de Gádor aquifer (SE Spain), are characterized by frequent and longtime dry periods, high temperatures and a strong dependence on groundwater. Campo de Dalías Groundwater body consist of a complex aquifer system, with 8 aquifers, some of them interconnected. The intense exploitation of groundwater (> 100 hm³/yr.) has caused a decrease in piezometric levels and water availability which affects water quantity and quality, with eventually episodes of marine intrusion. Clustering and different Machine Learning techniques can be very helpful for groundwater management and water table prediction.

Keywords: Clustering; water table prediction; water-stressed areas; Machine Learning.

1 INTRODUCTION

The semi-arid regions of the Mediterranean coast, such as Campo de Dalías and Sierra de Gádor aquifer (SE Spain), are characterized by frequent and long time periods of low rainfall, high temperatures and a strong dependence of groundwater. In the 80's, Campo de Dalías became one of the most intensive and productive agricultural areas in the world. Otherwise, the greenhouse's irrigation activity has progressively been increased totalizing nowadays more than 20.000 ha of greenhouses.

2 HYDROLOGICAL AND CLIMATE CONTEXT

A climate assessment has been carried out with data from 10 weather stations. The average rainfall for the period 1996/97-2018/19 is 301 mm/yr, with a predominance of dry and medium-dry years.

The most important water resource in Campo de Dalías area is groundwater, which is stored in detritic and karstic materials of Triassic, Miocene and Pliocene ages. The geological structure has a complex geometry, involving eight different aquifers, some of them interconnected. From an administrative point of view, they are all included in the Campo de Dalías and Sierra de Gádor Groundwater body (060.013). These aquifers can be divided in two classes: upper (unconfined) and lower (confined) aquifers.

From the 80's to the 90's of the last century the total groundwater demand has been increasing in all aquifers, upper and lower. Because of this intense groundwater exploitation for agriculture and the use of fertilizers, the shallow aquifer became to a bad chemical status. The groundwater resources were therefore substituted with surface water resources coming from the Benínar reservoir. From this moment on, most of the groundwater started to come from the deep aquifers (IGME, 2014).

According to the most recent Water Management Plan (DHCMA, 2020), the main water demand in groundwater body 060.013 is for agricultural use (146 hm³/yr.), followed by urban supply (47 hm³/yr.). From the total of irrigation demand, more than 60% correspond to groundwater resources and 20% correspond to surface water. Currently, new alternative water sources have been introduced to meet the water demand, like treated wastewater (8%) and desalinated water (5%).

3 RESULTS

In this study, funded by the European PRIMA call (**GOTHAM** on-going project), the impact of water availability on groundwater quantitative status at Campo de Dalías and Sierra de Gádor Groundwater Body has been assessed using Machine Learning techniques. Firstly, the missing values of the historical series have been completed using different methods, such as linear regression, mice forests, etc. Also, the values $\pm 10\%$ of variation between near values have been removed because they are considered outliers.

Then, Clustering techniques have been carried out to identify representative points of water table time series in each aquifer sector. The clustering method applied has been K-means using Dynamic Time Warping Matching metric. As a result of the 14 points available, 3 groups have been obtained (Figure 1) and 4 points have been left out due to the lack of continuity of the series. Also, 3 synthetic series have been developed as representative series of each group, that will be used for the water scarcity index estimation.

The input data used for the groundwater availability forecasting have been piezometric time series as the target variable (univariate approach). Moreover, to improve the goodness of fit of the predicted results, different Machine Learning algorithms (Linear Regression, XGBoost, SVR...) have been tested and the target variable (groundwater table) has been iterated with other explanatory variables (natural recharge in the aquifer and rainfall and temperature). The best results have been obtained using the target variable (accuracy $\approx 90\%$ in one step prediction while maintaining a good bias-variance ratio), while the explanatory variables do not significantly increase the accuracy. The results have been verified by analyzing the metrics (MAE, RMSE, etc.) in both the training and test sets, to avoid overfitting the models.

Figure 1. (left) Clustering map. (Right) Predictions using LR and SVR algorithms.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, from the results obtained, the classification by clusters has allowed us to classify piezometers according to their hydrodynamic behaviour where there is no hydrogeological information and to optimize the monitoring points. In addition, the accuracy of the results obtained for short-term prediction has been 90% and quite good for long-term predictions. However, for clusters 1 and 3 it will be necessary to add the explanatory variable of the season of the year. It also serves to anticipate possible future events and to cope with climate change. It has been demonstrated that the use of Machine Learning models is a very useful tool for efficient management of water resources in scenarios such as the one studied, where socio-economic activities are highly dependent on the availability of groundwater.

5 REFERENCES

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